

The Academy of Business in Society

Highlights Report 2019

Table of Contents

Introduction	3
About ABIS	4
Knowledge Into Action Forum	5
Partnership with Junior Enterprises Europe	6
Scenario Exploration System Workshops	7
The 18th ABIS Annual Colloquium 2019	8
Best Impact Startup Award	10
Publication of ABIS Special Issue	11
EU Research and Innovation Projects	12
The European Green Deal Report	15
Other Engagement Activities	16
Special Thank you	17
Activities for Q1 & Q2	18
Membership plans	19
ABIS Team and Board	21

Introduction

Dr. Ivo Matser EMP
Chief Executive Officer

Prof. Dr. Baback Yazdani
Chair of the Board of Directors

Dear ABIS Partners and Members,

It is a great pleasure to share with you our main activities of the last year 2019, that has seen a very constructive and purposeful involvement of our members.

We were pleased to have welcomed our network in May at the Knowledge into Action Forum hosted by our partner Unilever in London. Later in October, we celebrated our 18th anniversary at the 18th Annual Colloquium co-organized with our member ESMT Berlin, where we took stock of how much there is still to do, but also how far we have come in mainstreaming sustainability in business and academia.

True to our mission, we helped our partners and members to equip 350 young, talented students and junior entrepreneurs with mindsets and skills to accelerate the transition towards sustainable business models delivering 7 Scenario Exploration Workshops throughout the year. We continue our approach to create more dynamics together with young generations and movers and to bring more activities to our members. In this regard, we also partnered up with Junior Entreprises Europe (JEE) to engage junior entrepreneurs in our education and training initiatives.

We are happy to be broadening our business-academic membership to Sulapac- a Finnish start-up producing sustainable biodegradable packaging, that won our Best Impact Start-up Award at Colloquium.

Striving to be a positive force for change never stops. Therefore, in the beginning of 2020 we will submit our brand-new proposal to the H2020 funding opportunity on "Understanding the transition to a circular economy" with a carefully built consortium led by Antwerp Management School (AMS).

With the aim to disseminate our members knowledge, we are in the process of publishing a Special Issue on "Business in Society: Measuring Impact and Creating Change" with the research papers presented at the 18th Annual Colloquium with the collaboration of Emerald publishing.

In the meantime, within the EU funded project "ReTrace - Realizing the Transition towards the Circular Economy" we will be hosting event in order to bring together young researchers and businesses on circular economy topics. You can also expect our annual events Knowledge into Action Forum (KIAF) in May and 19th Annual Colloquium in October. We are also planning more smaller scale events and activities tailored to specific needs.

We are deeply touched by discouraging news and lots of pessimistic views of what is happening in the world around us. This is not to argue, of course. However, we are also inspired by the new, brave voices of the young generation, the encouraging actions taken by business and promising research from academia that bring the potential for change and impact in our community. We are convinced that there is more that is possible than people would expect from the past. Together, we can make the difference for the prosperity of our planet and future.

Dr. Ivo Matser EMP
Chief Executive Officer

Prof. Baback Yazdani
Chair of the Board of Directors

About ABIS

Who we are

ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society is a business-academic network working together to advance the role of business in society through research and education. Our ambition is to make a significant contribution to the debate and the practice involved in equipping current and future business leaders with the knowledge, skills and capabilities for the long-term success of business in society.

Our story

ABIS was founded in 2001 and launched at INSEAD in 2002 with the support of the leading Business Schools in Europe (INSEAD, IMD, London, ESADE, IESE, Copenhagen, Warwick, Vlerick, Ashridge, Cranfield, Bocconi) in partnership with IBM, Microsoft, Johnson & Johnson, Unilever and Shell. This initiative was driven by a shared belief that challenges linked to globalization and sustainable development required new management skills, mindsets & capabilities. ABIS developed a strong role in responding to this need and it focused on integrating sustainability at the heart of business curricula, corporate policies and business strategies by providing knowledge and capacity building.

Our network

Our network is unique as it is big enough to have always new insights and ideas flowing, but small enough to create intimate atmosphere and build long lasting and strong connections with each other. We are one of very few business-academic networks, fostering this relationship as we are convinced that research and business is inseparable, and that academia and business need to work together to create a sustainable world. We are proud to claim that our members are willing to share openly their challenges and dilemmas to learn and further progress. This creates an inclusive community and environment where individuals feel safe to share and value each other insights and experiences in order to scale up the efforts in research, education and promoting sustainable ways of doing business.

We believe that the value is in the network and we achieve it with and for our members through:

3 main engagement areas

Knowledge Productivity

ABIS collaborates with its members by gathering and absorbing relevant knowledge and using it to develop new research engagement activities, building peer-to-peer sharing, thought leadership and mono or multidisciplinary dialogues.

Learning & Development

ABIS leverages knowledge and insights to co-create learning, skills development and capacity building platforms to equip current & future leaders with the mindsets and skills they need to contribute to sustainable development.

Communication & Dissemination

ABIS leverages the connections with our members to share and spread the latest and most relevant research, insights and initiatives for and from our members.

Knowledge Into Action Forum

"Driving Sustainable Innovation to Deliver Impact"

On May 22nd, the 2019 Knowledge Into Action Forum (KIAF) brought together the ABIS network and relevant stakeholders to discuss and collaborate on how to drive innovation by putting sustainability at the core of business and research practices. The KIAF offered a platform to present innovative ideas and initiatives, as well as the opportunity to create new partnerships for research and innovation projects.

The KIAF took place at the Unilever International Management Training Centre Four Acres nearby London, where we had the opportunity to connect with the best global sustainability and innovation experts from the academic and business world.

To build on our conversations from the 17th Annual Colloquium and to create safe space for open discussions on topics that matter to our members, we launched several webinars that preceded KIAF. The aim was to bring people together on relevant topics that could generate ideas for our Innovation Forum at Knowledge Into Action Forum in spring 2019.

- Webinar on Digitalization and New Business Value
- Webinar on Anonymity of Data
- Webinar on Sustainable Finance: Improving Regulation and Engaging Shareholders
- Webinar on Role of Circular Economy in rethinking plastics

We introduced an innovative form at our KIAF which consisted of two parts, knowledge sharing morning and a learning afternoon. In the morning corporate and academic speakers addressed the drivers and enablers of sustainable innovation. In the afternoon we aimed to investigate, explore and implement sustainable solutions to challenges and dilemmas of our members. The Innovation Forum consisted of a pitching session that gave the opportunity to the selected speakers to tease on a challenge that needed to be discussed and worked on. The KIAF participants had then the opportunity to choose on which challenge to work on and split into different breakout sessions. Based on a recognized methodology of Idea Crowd Sourcing, the NOW-HOW-WOW Matrix and the Project Vision Board the groups were able to engage with a community of sustainability experts and have a moment of a stimulating ideas creation for future collaboration and project creation. The following organizations brought forward the challenges discussed:

- **Unilever:** Enabling access to safe water in the emerging markets
- **Mazars:** Sustainable reporting and auditing model to address societal needs beyond 2020
- **Copenhagen Business School:** Fostering sustainable innovation through pay-for-success models
- **The Carbon Literacy Project:** Scaling up the Engagement and Action on Climate Change
- **Tech4Impact:** Leveraging Technologies to Address Grand Societal Challenges
- **JEToP:** Engaging Junior Enterprises in Open Innovation Initiatives for SMEs

The KIAF was followed by a General Assembly led by Alfons Sauquet Rovira as his last engagement as the Chair of Board of Directors of ABIS. The 4 years were steered successfully thanks to his active guidance.

Partnership with Junior Enterprises Europe (JE Europe)

True to our goal to be involved in the practice of equipping current and future business leaders with the knowledge, skills and capabilities for the long-term success of business in society, we signed a Memorandum of Understanding with the Junior Enterprises Europe (JE Europe, formerly known as JADE European Confederation of Junior Enterprises).

JE Europe is a non-profit umbrella organization that represents more than 28 000 students of higher education institutions, currently working in 330 student-led organizations in 14 countries across Europe. These organizations, also known as Junior Enterprises, are the environment where students can develop their entrepreneurial skills while being at university by providing more than 4350 consultancy projects to SMEs every year.

The aim of our partnership is to combine our expertise and knowledge to the implementation of the UN Sustainable Development Goals with a multi-stakeholder partnership focused on the training of future leaders. Since the beginning of our collaboration we engage junior entrepreneurs in education and training initiatives to develop mindsets and skills required to accelerate the transition towards sustainable business models, combining business growth with positive impact through our Scenario Exploration workshops - Building Leadership for Sustainability .

ABIS' CEO Ivo Matser agreed to join JEE Advisory Board to support their activities on a strategic level in order to contribute to each other's strategy development and governance.

Scenario Exploration System Workshops

Building Leadership for Sustainability

The Scenario Exploration System is a serious gaming platform developed by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre to facilitate the practical use of scenarios from foresight studies.

The "Building Leadership for Sustainability" version developed by ABIS engages learners in a role-play simulation to develop mindsets and skills required to thrive in an increasingly complex business environment, while simultaneously contributing to long-term social, environmental and economic goals. The methodology of the game enables the acquisition of a solid understanding of sustainable development through an interactive process that integrates sustainability into the long-term strategies of different stakeholders.

The purpose of each workshop is to enable participants to experience and act through plausible sustainable alternative futures, by thinking and conversing outside of their usual frame of reference. The aim is not to play a game and win, but rather to promote a constructive conversation among key societal actors and to promote integrated long-term thinking in a spirit of collaboration.

Since 2018, the workshop has been increasingly popular among the ABIS network and beyond. Throughout the year 2019 we delivered 8 workshops at Cranfield School of Management, Brussels School of International Studies - University of Kent, JEE Europe Spring & Summer Conference, Westminster University, Politecnico di Milano, Politecnico di Torin and ESADE Business School.

We offer to our members the opportunity to co-design a workshop session and to use the Scenario Exploration System as part of teaching modules, training activities and other relevant events. The Westminster University with their junior enterprise Westminster Business Consultants co-developed a Scenario Exploration System workshop as an assessment tool for their future consultants. They believe this tool helped them to assess the participants in a more thorough way and the whole process took even shorter than before.

Besides enabling a better understanding of sustainable development and the complexities of socio-economic systems, this game-based methodology requires participants to use a series of soft skills that are considered critical for responsible leaders such as negotiation skills, creativity, emotional intelligence, problem solving and critical thinking.

We were able to collect data from 110 participants of our workshops, who filled in our carefully designed two-part survey. The respondents were asked to fill in one part of the survey before the start of the workshop and one afterwards. In the order to assess their perception of used and developed skills throughout the workshop.

The findings provide important insight into how the learners perceive their soft skills development and the overall perception of the workshop. The findings showcase that the students perceived to use and develop each of the soft skills mentioned as a result of engaging in discussions and systemic thinking during the game. When asked which of the skills they used during the workshop the most, critical thinking and creativity were the most frequently mentioned.

The 18th ABIS Annual Colloquium 2019

Business in Society: Measuring Impact and Creating Change

In the light of the 30th anniversary of the fall of the Berlin Wall and the 18 years since the foundation of ABIS - The Academy of Business in Society, the ABIS Annual Colloquium 2019 represented a significant opportunity to reflect on the striking changes the world has experienced over the last 3 decades. We were invited by our long-term member ESMT Berlin to their historic main building in Berlin, which formerly housed the State Council of the East Germany.

85 participants representing 50 organisations from 20+ countries joined us to discuss "Business in Society: Measuring Impact and Creating Change". We offered a platform for high level discussions with our business-academic network on the importance of measuring impact, the challenges that academia and business are facing to maximize their impact and share best practices that create positive change for reaching the SDGs.

The first day of our Colloquium highlighted that the traditional Business in Society paradigm is changing in the era of UN SDGs. Companies are transforming themselves from a commonly shared and established model towards a more advanced "corporate sustainability", not only searching for immediate "win-win" solutions, but aiming to achieve truly shared triple bottom line value creation

We also dived in a panel discussion on "Business in Society: Trends and Academic Insights" with academic experts representing 4 different universities and 3 different countries. The panel reflected on the developments of corporate responsibility from "nice to have" to strategic and operational integration and business action towards the SDGs. The discussions steered towards drivers of advancing sustainable development, but also the challenges that businesses and academia are facing. One of the main challenges remains impact measurement and with that the lack and quality of data and different frameworks and approaches. All of the speakers agreed that academia and business need to work closely together to overcome barriers and to accomplish the comprehensive sustainability goals in a way that will ensure translation of the latest knowledge in a relevant and applicable manner into impactful innovation.

The panel was followed by a review of the most recent and innovative research presented in 3 different tracks by 16 purposeful academics:

1. Assessing and measuring business impact
2. Drivers and barriers to sustainability and SDG implementation
3. New Approaches to sustainable value and creation

The 18th ABIS Annual Colloquium 2019

Business in Society: Measuring Impact and Creating Change

The second day of Colloquium began by challenging the current "business as usual" approaches and called for a deep socio-economic system change needed to tackle the complex societal challenges we are facing - climate crisis, biodiversity loss, inequality, poverty, migration. Among the others, such paradigm shift will require true corporate citizenship, long-termism and a higher degree of innovation across multiple dimensions.

Growth-at-all-cost models and the way success has been measured in our economy and business are now coming at the expense of our ability to thrive. A growing number of companies are taking steps to be more responsible in how they treat employees, customers, communities and the planet. We had the chance to listen to the reasons and drivers behind Patagonia's embodiment of sustainable and purposeful business, their new mission and their activities to support regenerative agriculture, fighting climate change and even engaging in bold political stances.

We welcomed high level corporate representatives from Danone, Novo Nordisk, Accenture and Danske Bank who shared their knowledge and insights during a panel discussion on "Growing with Positive Impact". They reflected on the importance of challenging conventional thinking to support and inspire people to think differently as the only way how progress can be made. Businesses must set a strategy even when they don't know how to get there and they also need to execute fast even if it means to trial and sometimes fail.

The panel session was followed by two sets of interactive breakout sessions addressing "Measuring impact" and "Creating Change", that allowed participants to dive into more focused and specific topics:

- Interactive session 1.1: Measuring climate performance - 2° Investing Initiative
- Interactive session 1.2: Impact assessment and value balancing - Value Balancing Alliance
- Interactive session 2.1: Impactful partnership with startups - Enel
- Interactive session 2.2: Transforming business for the SDGs - Accenture

Best Impact Startup Award

Sulapac was awarded as the Best Impact Startup

This year's Colloquium was also about bringing innovation and positive inspiration to our business-academic network. Therefore, we organized a Best Impact Startup Award to reward purpose-led startups in finding creative ways to solve social and environmental problems while simultaneously growing their business.

First we launched a call for nominations for start-ups to apply by describing their business activities and demonstrating positive impact in social, environmental or financial aspects.

The ABIS team carefully selected the top 3 finalists considering the scope of impact, the level of innovation, positive contribution to society and stakeholder engagement that were then invited for a 5 minute pitching competition in front of our audience at the 18th Annual Colloquium in Berlin. The 3 finalists were:

- Resourcify - a digital platform for recycling
- Value for Good - a purpose driven consultancy in social impact
- Sulapac - a producer of biodegradable packaging material

The Colloquium audience, which consisted of sustainability experts from our business and academic network, civil society organization and junior enterprises awarded the best startup by live online voting.

The winner of our Best Impact Startup Award is Sulapac - a producer of biodegradable and microplastic-free material made entirely from renewable sources and certified wood. Sulapac was acknowledged to positively contributing to sustainable development and inspiring others to do the same. They were awarded a full ABIS institutional membership for a year, a private meeting with the Managing Director & Sustainability Strategy Practice Lead of Accenture, Alexander Holst and a 3D printed material prize which was handed over by our CEO, Ivo Matser.

With a mission to save the world from plastic waste, microplastic-free materials must become the new normal. To make this vision reality, Sulapac has taken a very open, active and collaborative approach. *"To find a way out from the plastic waste crisis, we need to join forces and get activated on all levels of society, across industries and disciplines"*, states Sulapac's Sustainability Director Maija Pohjakallio, who attended our Colloquium.

Sulapac® is a wood-based material innovation, which is a lot like plastic, yet it biodegrades fully leaving no microplastics behind. As a premium material that is safe and circular by design. Plastic product manufacturers can use Sulapac® with their existing machinery making sustainability an easy choice. The company was founded in 2016 by Suvi Haimi and Laura Tirkkonen-Rajasalo and is based in Helsinki, Finland.

Suvi Haimi, Sulapac Co-founder and CEO commented on their victory *"We are extremely delighted for this recognition, as the award carries an important message that reflects Sulapac's philosophy. We are solving major environmental problem and the principles of sustainable development are incorporated in everything we do. At the same time, we need to create profitable business."*

Publication of ABIS Special Issue

on "Business in Society: Measuring Impact and Creating Change"

There is a lack of a common standard for measuring business impact and externalities on society and nature. The amount and quality of information provided by companies varies. It remains very complicated to measure and understand a company's biodiversity footprint and the same applies for social impact indicators. This is also problematic for investors, which find it extremely difficult to direct funding to companies which represent good investments in the long-term – for both shareholders and society. This represents a big challenge that business are facing in maximizing their positive impact on society. Advancing the role of business in society requires more relevant research, knowledge and new management and leadership skills, mindsets and capabilities.

That is why, we partnered up with Emerald Group Publishing to create a Special Issue on Business in Society: Measuring Impact and Creating Change for the Journal Corporate Governance, The international journal of business in society.

The Special Issue seeks to advance our knowledge on the state-of-the art of business in society and how impact measurement and the growing role of investors and start-ups can further accelerate positive impact and create value for society.

To ensure the quality of the publication we chose to work with top academics that took on the role as Guest Editors: Ivo Matser ABIS & Gisma Business School, Yury Blagov, St. Petersburg University; Thomas Osburg, Fresenius University of Applied Sciences and Boleslaw Rok, Kozminski University.

From disseminating our Call for Papers, we received a considerable amount of paper abstracts from which we selected 16 papers that best fit the scope of the theme of our Colloquium and future publication.

The 16 authors of the research papers were then invited to present their paper proposals and the outcomes of their research at the 18th Annual Colloquium in Berlin. We identified 3 main tracks for this purpose, chaired by 3 academic experts in the fields: Lin Lerpold, Ivo Matser and Thomas Osburg.

1. Assessing and measuring business impact
2. Drivers and barriers to sustainability and SDG implementation
3. New Approaches to sustainable value and creation

At this moment in time, we collected interests from our network to act as reviewers for the double blind peer review - a necessary part of publishing. The authors submitted their finalized research papers and we are continuing reviewing them with the help of our academic partners and their excessive experience and skills in the field. The expected publication of our Special Issue is in the summer 2020.

EU Research and Innovation Projects

ReTrace: Realizing the Transition to the Circular Economy

Since 2018, we are part of a consortium led by University of Sheffield in EU Horizon 2020 project under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) called "ReTrace" - Realizing the Transition to the Circular Economy. The consortium is composed of University of Sheffield, Università Degli Studi di Napoli Parthenope, Universitaet Kassel, SEERC, ABIS, Hogskolan Dalarna, University of Kent, TATA Steel UK, Olympia Electronics and Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam. The partners also include University of Exeter, Leeds University Business School, University of Ulsan and Shanghai Jiao Tong University.

The main aim of the ReTraCE project is the creation of a cohort of professionals capable of driving the transition towards the Circular Economy (CE) and employable not only by research institutions, but also by public sector bodies (e.g. local authorities and national agencies) and manufacturing and service sectors including: metals industry, electric and electronic equipment manufacturing, construction materials and waste management.

The main innovation of the project is the development of a holistic approach for evaluating and realizing the transition towards the Circular Economy, involving knowledge and methodologies from multiple domains (including Supply Chain Management, Environmental Science, Environmental and Ecological Economics, Science and Technology Studies, Innovation Studies) and addressing economic, environmental and social issues. The trans-national, multi-disciplinary, multi-sector, multi-stakeholder approach proposed in this project aims to bridge the main gap in research dealing with the CE paradigm, that, to date, has been characterized by a "silo" approach that has undermined theoretical developments and knowledge transfer to practitioners.

The consortium designed and delivers world class multidisciplinary training to 15 Early Stage Researchers (ESRs) offering them an extended and valuable program of international exchanges and secondments through the wide network of partner organisations from public, private and third sectors involved in the proposal.

One of these 15 researchers is Josep Pinyol, who is hosted by ABIS since May 2019. He is also enrolled in the PhD programme in Sustainable Futures at the University of Exeter Business School and is conducting research on the impact of the political discourse of circular economy in environmental policy making.

Within the project, part of the key responsibilities of ABIS is to organize 2 project meetings with the researchers and consortium bridging them with industry experts, in May and October 2020 in Brussels.

The first project meeting will take place on 11 - 12.05.2020 and will be connected to the ABIS Knowledge Into Action Forum 2020. The two events will be closely intertwined by the common focus on Circular Economy. The attendance to ReTrace meeting will include a free participation in the Knowledge Into Action Forum.

ReTraCE

REALISING THE TRANSITION TOWARDS THE CIRCULAR ECONOMY

EU Research and Innovation Projects

H2020 Proposal on Circular Economy

Greening the economy in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)

Since October 2019, we have been building a consortium to apply for EU funding opportunity of a Horizon 2020 Call on "Understanding the transition to a circular economy and its implications on the environment, economy and society" in February 2020. The institutional leader of the project is Antwerp Management School with ABIS acting as a bridge and management support for other business and academic institutions involved. The consortium consists of 13 academic members.

- Alliance Manchester Business School
- ALTIS Milano
- Bocconi University
- Copenhagen Business School
- ESADE
- ESMT Berlin
- Kigali University
- Kozminski University
- Rokskilde University
- Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences
- St. Gallen University
- University of Stellenbosch Business School
- University of Turku

The success of the project will rely on the engagement with corporates involved in the transition to circular economy. Companies will be heavily involved in the process and at this time the consortium is contacting companies which should be part of it.

The research will assess the current state of transition towards the circular economy in relevant economic sectors (public, private and non-profit) and analyse possible transition scenarios, as well as their outcomes and impacts. It will identify the key factors (regulatory, governance-based, market, technological, cultural, societal, gender, etc.) that can stimulate or hinder this transition.

The project results are expected to contribute to:

- more systemic policy decisions to further facilitate the transition to a safe, environmentally friendly, efficient and effective circular economy in selected sectors, efficient and effective use of both primary and secondary resources in Europe, reducing waste generation, negative health impacts, environmental pollution and greenhouse gas emissions;
- new business opportunities for European industries and SMEs; creating new tools and methodologies oriented to companies, to consider social, environmental and economic aspects when they design circular business models;
- creating incentives and support the development of strategic governance mechanisms that enable the transition to a Circular Economy and contribute to the effective implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals in Europe;
- supporting the achievement of climate commitments and specific quantitative targets on resources efficiency, recycling rates or waste disposal quotas.

EU Research and Innovation Projects

Sustainability for SMEs' organisational optimisation

In March 2019 ABIS joined a consortium to apply for an EU funding proposal "Sustainability for SMEs organisational optimisation", which aims to increase SMEs abilities in demonstrating their commitment to sustainability and responsible business practices.

The consortium consists of

- **RRIF** College of Financial Management (Croatia)
- **ABIS** (Belgium)
- **EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY CYPRUS** (Cyprus)
- **SK SUSTAINABILITY KNOWLEDGE GROUP LTD** (Cyprus)
- **MB "Homo Eminens" Lithuania** (Lithuania)

The overall aim of the SustainSME project is to increase SMEs' ability in demonstrating their commitment to sustainability and responsible business practices. The purpose of the products proposed by the SustainSME partner is to foster SMEs ability to integrate sustainability thinking/acting into all levels of their organizations by offering tailored training solutions and specialised support via e-learning platforms. This is directly connected with policies as the EU 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, Paris Agreement, Conflict Materials Directive, Directive of NFR and GDPR are some of the new sustainability standards for business sustainability and will have a huge impact on all organisations and the European community.

The partners aim at offering a proper combination of theoretical and practical approaches and extending the national 'vision' to the European 'vision' in line with the EU 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. A transnational partnership among a university, VET providers, experts in ESG reporting and SMEs consultants, ensures a strong team that can lead EU SMEs toward better and more responsible and sustainable business.

Horizon 2020 Transformative Knowledge and Skills for Higher Impact

ABIS also took part in a consortium with 7 academic institutions and training centres from 9 countries applying for an EU funding opportunity under the Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks program. The proposal addresses Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Area Studies (InTrAS): Transformative Knowledge and Skills for Higher Impact Global Cooperation and Development.

The proposal led by University of Basel combines a doctoral programme that trains young scholars on how to translate their research into policy with a research agenda inquiring into the relationship between global development knowledge and its transformative potential. It will examine the role of values and interests in policy design and implementation in order to produce transformative knowledge and equip 11 early-stage researchers with the transformative skills to increase the impact of global cooperation for development.

InTrAS aims at:

- 1) Designing research approaches that support evidence-based policy by directly applying them in areas central to the design of European development and international relations policy (democracy and good governance, public health, peace and security) while, at the same time, have the transformative potential to contribute to keeping Europe's status as a front-runner in the implementation of the UN Agenda 2030;
- 2) Training a nucleus of next-generation researchers both living up to highest scientific standards and able to make an impact in various fields such as development cooperation, consulting, corporate social responsibility, humanitarian aid, diplomacy or media.

The European Green Deal Report

The European Green Deal is a response to environment related challenges that Europe and the whole world are facing. It is the new growth strategy that aims to transform the EU and become carbon neutral by 2050. This is an opportunity to put Europe firmly on a new path of sustainable and inclusive growth.

The environmental ambition of the Green Deal will not be achieved by the EU alone. New and strong partnerships created by purposeful leaders, future-fit businesses and relevant stakeholders will be critical. The SDG17 - Partnerships for the goals is crucial to move forward and achieve our goals.

For 18 years, ABIS has been working on bridging the academic and business world to support research and education towards sustainable development. We are therefore uniquely positioned to contribute to successfully transforming the EU's economy for a sustainable future.

In this spirit, we have published a special **European Green Deal report** to bring our network the information about the initial roadmap of the key policies and measures on the EU's strategy to implement the United Nation 2030 Agenda and reach the Sustainable Development Goals. The report was presented at the Antwerp Management School for the MBA program.

Other engagement activities

Business School Rankings Report

ABIS contributed to the creation of the report on "Business School Ranking for the 21st Century" launched at the World Economic Forum in 2019, that suggests changes in the methodology of rankings to align with the needs of the 21st century. The report, published under the aegis of the UN Global Compact, suggests to incorporate criteria that measure ESG factors within the core curricula.

27th CEEMAN Conference

ABIS CEO, Ivo Matser, represented ABIS at the 27th CEEMAN Annual Conference on Management Education for a Changing World. He was the moderator of the roundtable on "What Should Management Schools Do Differently than at Present to Prepare Managers for the Opportunities and Threats of AI?"

PRME RMER Conference

ABIS was present at the 6th RMER (Responsible Management Education Research) Conference hosted by Jönköping International Business School (JIBS) to engage the PRME community in a dialogue around Agenda 2030 and enhance further collaborations in education, research and business practices to advance the SDGs.

Spring Research Days at GSEM Ekaterinburg

In March 2019, Ivo Matser held a workshop during the Spring Research Days at the Graduate School of Economics and Management in Ekaterinburg, Russia where experts discussed the global trends of sustainable development principles influencing current business models in the context of digitalization.

University of Kent, Brussels Study Tour

In February 2019, For the management program of University of Kent "Brussels Study Tour" Ivo Matser held a presentation on "Leading Change and Business Culture" followed by a Scenario Exploration System Workshop.

EU Green Deal Presentation at AMS

Marco Matrisciano, Research Project & Funding Manager presented the European Green Deal report to the MBA students at the Antwerp Management School. He shared the initial roadmap of the key policies and measures on the EU's strategy to implement the United Nations' 2030 Agenda and reach the Sustainable Development Goals.

JE Europe Spring Conference

ABIS had the pleasure to be in the jury of the JE Excellence Awards and have the possibility to award the Best International Junior Enterprise. At the JE Europe Spring Conference in Brussels in March 2019. We also hosted a very stimulating Scenario Exploration System Workshop. .

OIKOS International FutureLab

Ivo Matser was invited as a speaker to the Oikos International FutureLab taking place in Geneva in November 2019. He addressed the topic "Building partnerships for changing economics and management education" taking place in Geneva.

Alliance with GRLI

In Spring 2019, ABIS welcomed GRLI (Globally Responsible Leadership Initiative) to discuss about our strategic goals and the ways how we can support each other in our activities. We were pleased strengthen our relations with the representatives of GRLI - John North and Claire Maxwell.

GSOM Emerging Markets Conference

Ivo Matser took the role of a chair of the track on "Business in Society: A Change of Paradigm" together with our Board Member Yury Blagov at the 6th International Emerging Market Conference at GSOM St. Petersburg University in October 2019.

Special Thank you

We are listing names and companies that were actively engaged in the network activities and contributed as speakers at our events and webinars, co-creators and designers of our initiatives and projects, researchers as well as companies and organizations who raised difficult questions and are open for collaborations. We would like to dedicate these lines for you as a thank you for believing in us, embracing the ABIS spirit and making us want to strive for more.

Clive Allison - Global Director, Innovation & New Business Models, Unilever

Joseph Amankwah-Amoah - Associate Professor, Kent Business School

Jan Beyne - Researcher, Antwerp Management School

Elisabeth Bigand - Secretary General, JE Europe

Julia Binder - Deputy of the Vice President for Innovation & Head of Tech4Impact, EPFL

Yury Blagov - Director, PwC Center for CSR, Graduate School of Management St. Petersburg University

Laurent Bontoux - Foresight Specialist, Joint Research Centre, European Commission

Tamer Boyaci - Dean of Faculty, Professor of Management Science, ESMT Berlin

Felipe Calderon - Head of Washington SyCip Graduate School of Business, Asian Institute of Management

Anthony Carey - Partner, Mazars

Diogo Carriço - Former Secretary General, JEE Europe

Fiona Charnley - Associate Professor of Circular Economy, University of Exeter

Ernesto Ciorra - Chief Innovability Officer, Enel

Dave Coleman - Managing Director, The Carbon Literacy Project

Ephraim Daka - Doctoral Candidate, Turku School of Economics

Joel Diener - Scientific Assistant, Catholic University of Eichstaett-Ingolstadt

Niall Dunne - CEO, Polymateria

Ismail Erturk - Senior Lecturer, Alliance Manchester Business School

Marc Fiammante - Distinguished Engineer & Leader of the Europe Federal CTO team, IBM

Isabella Florio - Former Vice President, JEE Europe

Paul Francis - Director, Max Planck Institute for Software Systems

Isabel Galvis - Doctoral Candidate, Turku School of Economics

Ryan Gellert - General Manager EMEA, Patagonia

David Gomez - Former President, JEE Europe

Mark Griffiths - Global Leader Climate Business Hub, WWF

Lisa Gring-Pemble - Associate Professor, George Mason University

Ulrika Hasselgren - Global Head of Sustainability & Impact Investment, Danske Bank

Jacqueline Hochreiter - Sustainability Lead Europe, AB InBev

Alexander Holst - Managing Director & Sustainability Lead for the DACH Region, Accenture Strategy

Peter Hopkinson - Director, University of Exeter Centre for Circular Economy

Patrick Hull - Strategy Director

CHRO Office, Unilever

Michel Kalika - Director BSIS, EFMD

Susanne Klages - Model Lead, Value Balancing Alliance

Dmitri Khatko - Senior Lecturer, GSOM St. Petersburg University

Yanina Kowszyk - Research Affiliate, University of Barcelona

Alex Lanaro - Former Treasurer, JEE Europe

Lin Lerpold - Associate Professor, Stockholm School of Economics & Vice Chair Board of Directors, AP2

Natacha

Lopes - Vice President, JE Europe

Chris Loxley - Former Project Leader, Global R&D, Unilever & Head of Research, LovedBy Design

Eugenio Massini - Head of Sales, JETOP

Emujin Munkh-Erdene - Managing Director, Westminster Business Consultants

Clare Murray - Analyst, 2° Investing Initiative (2°ii)

Eva Niesten - Senior Lecturer, Alliance Manchester Business School

Okechukwu Okorie - Postdoctoral Research Associate, University of Exeter

Thomas Osburg - Dean of Studies 'Automotive & Mobility Management', Head of Competence Center Entrepreneurship, Fresenius University of Applied Sciences

David Palazzetti - Deputy Head of Sales, JETOP

Rashik Parmar - Technical Executive, IBM

Esben Pedersen - Professor, Copenhagen Business School

Francesco Perrini - Professor, SDA Bocconi School of Management

Alexia Perversi - Director, Mazars

Anastasia Petrova-Savchenko - Senior Lecturer, GSOM St. Petersburg University

Jonatan Pinkse - Executive Director, Manchester Institute of Innovation Research, Alliance Manchester Business School

Joanna Radeke - Manager Center for Sustainable Business and Leadership, ESMT Berlin

Mikael Rantanen - Human Resources Manager, Westminster Business Consultants

Boleslaw Rok - Professor, Kozminski University

Alfons Sauquet Rovira - Former Chair of the Board of Directors, ABIS & Professor, ESADE Business School

Florian Schildheuer - President, Junior Enterprises Europe

Anton Schwarz - Treasurer, JE Europe

Domenico Spadavecchia - Law Department Manager, Westminster Business Consultants

Katharina Stenholm - Senior Vice President, Chief of Cycles and Procurement Officer, Danone

Susanne Stormer - Vice President Corporate Sustainability, Novo Nordisk

Jakob Thomae - Managing Director, 2° Investing Initiative

Ailbhe Timmons - Manager Employee EMEA, Johnson & Johnson

Arjen van Klink - Program Director, Rotterdam University of Applied Sciences

Wayne Visser - Professor, Antwerp Management School

Gavin Warner - Director Sustainable Business, Unilever

Rosina Watson - Senior Lecturer, Cranfield School of Management

Rachel West - Vice President, Westminster Business Consultants

Activities for Q1 & Q2 2020

Striving to be a positive force for change never stops. Therefore, we are pleased to share our activities planned for the first half of 2020. We invite you to reach out to the ABIS team on how you can engage.

January 2020

Scenario Exploration System Workshop
Henley Business School

17.02.2020

Scenario Exploration System Workshop
Kent Business School

26.02.2020

Participation in JEE Winter Conference 27.02.2020

- Participation in the "JEE Excellence Award" Jury for the "Most Sustainable Junior Enterprise"
- Scenario Exploration System Workshop

Creating Value Roundtable
Antwerp Management School

20.04.2020

Re-Trace - Meeting the Industry

11 - 12.05.2020

13.05.2020 Knowledge Into Action Forum 2020

KIAF

Circular Economy

June 2020

Membership plans

In 2019 we updated our Membership plans, adding two new categories to the existing partnership and membership - Associate Institutional Membership for members that would like to collaborate with us for the first time and Individual Membership for people who would like to benefit from our network and activities not interlinked with their organisation.

On top of our four classic memberships we also offer **Affiliate Memberships**, that are strategic alliances with international associations, NGOs, start-ups and junior enterprises that share the same values and beliefs and help us accelerate the transition for a more inclusive and sustainable world.

ABIS Team and Board

ABIS Team

Dr. Ivo Matser EMP
Chief Executive Officer

Marco Matrisciano
Research Projects and Funding Manager

Karolina Sobczak
Member Relations and Data Manager

Katarina Haluskova
Project Communication Specialist

Mafous Lassissi
Office Manager & Executive Assistant

Josep Pinyol
Early Stage Researcher
H2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie
Circular Economy

ABIS Board of Directors

Prof. Dr. Baback Yazdani
Chair of the Board of Directors &
Dean of Nottingham Business School

Manuela Brusoni
Associate Professor
SDA Bocconi School of Management

Yury E. Blagov
Director, Center for Corporate Social Responsibility
Graduate School of Management,
St. Petersburg University

Joan Fontrodona
Full Professor
IESE Business School

Adrie Heninbroek
Principal Responsible Investment
NN Investment Partners

David Herbinet
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Gary Kildare
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